

**THE PRESENT SIMPLE TENSE
(ODDIY HOZIRGI ZAMON)**

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Ingliz tili o'qituvchilari

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Annotatsiya. Bu maqolada The Present Simple haqida ma'lumot keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: The Present Simple, Subject, Verb.

The Present Simple Tens zamonini doimiy yoki qaytarilib turadigan ish harakatga nisbatan ishlatiladi.

Masalan: I go to school everyday. Men har kuni maktabga boraman.

You work at the hospital. Siz shifoxonada ishlaysiz.

Biz Present Simple zamonida 3-shaxs birlik (he, she, it)dan keyin keladigan fe'llar uchun -s yoki -es qo'shimchalarini qo'shamiz.

He goes to school everyday

My mother (she) works at the school.

Present simple yasash uchun quyidagi formuladan foydalanamiz:

Subject + Verb (III+es) + Object

I + work + at the University

He + goes + to school everyday

Inkor gap yasaganimizda egadan keyin do not (don't) yoki does not (doesn't) qo'yamiz.

I don't like ice cream

Tom (he) doesn't work at school

Present Simple

Affirmative	Negative	
	Long form	Short Form
I walk	I do not walk	I don't walk
You walk	You do not walk	You don't walk
He walks	He does not walk	He doesn't walk
She walks	She does not walk	She doesn't walk
It walks	It does not walk	It doesn't walk
We walk	We do not walk	We don't walk
You walk	You do not walk	You don't walk
They walk	They do not walk	They don't walk

We use the **present simple** for repeated actions or permanent situations.

Spelling of 3rd person singular for verbs ending in:

ss, sh, ch, x, o + es	consonant + y → ies	vowel + y + s
I brush - he brushes	I cry - he cries	I play - he plays

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III shaxs birlikka s yoki es qo'shamiz deb aytdik. Agar fe'limiz ss, sh, ch, x, o bilan tugasa es qo'shamiz.

rush – rushes

brush – brushes

do – does

Undosh harf + y bilan tugasa ies qo'shamiz.

cry – cries

fly – flies

Qolgan undosh harflar bilan tugasa s qo'shamiz.

know – knows

walk – walks

So'roq gap yasaganimizda esa biz doim egadan oldinga **Do** yoki III-shaxs birlik uchun **Does** ni qo'yamiz.

Do you work at the hospital?

Does she speak English?

Quyidagi jadvada savol tuzish va unga qisqa javob berish jadvali keltirilgan: ¹

Interrogative	Short Answers
Do I walk?	Yes, I do . / No, I don't .
Do you walk?	Yes, you do . / No, you don't .
Does he walk?	Yes, he does . / No, he doesn't .
Does she walk?	Yes, she does . / No, she doesn't .
Does it walk?	Yes, it does . / No, it doesn't .
Do we walk?	Yes, we do . / No, we don't .
Do you walk?	Yes, you do . / No, you don't .
Do they walk?	Yes, they do . / No, they don't .

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The Present Simple Tense (Oddiy hozirgi zamon)

Bu zamon odatda yoki har doim takrorlanib turadigan ish-harakatni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi.

1. Present Simple ning 3-shaxs birlikdan tashqari barcha shakllari fe'ning asosiy shaklini, (infi nitivning to yuklamasi tushirib qoldirilgan shaklini) qo'yish bilan yasaladi. 3-shaxs birlikda fe'ning asosiy shakliga -s qo'shimchasi qo'shildi:

¹ <https://hasanboy.uz/14-dars-present-simple/>

to work - I (we, you, they) work, he works.

3-shaxs birlik qo'shimchasi -s jarangli undosh tovushlar va unlilar dan keyin [z], jarangsiz undosh tovushlardan keyin [s] deb o'qiladi:

He reads. He sees. He writes.

3-shaxs birlikda ss, ch, sh, x harfl ar (sirg'aluvchi tovushlar) bilan tugagan fe'llarga -es qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi va [iz] deb o'qiladi:

I pass - he passes, I dress - he dresses, I teach - he teaches, I wish - he wishes.

Izoh: Oldida undosh harfi bo'lgan - y harfi bilan tugagan fe'llarga 3-shaxs birlikda - es qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi va y harfi i harfiga aylanadi:

I cry - he cries: Men yig'ladim - U yig'ladi.

I carry - he carries: Men olib bordim - U olib bordi.

Oldida unli harfi bo'lgan y harfi bilan tugagan fe'llarga 3-shaxs birlikda umumiy qoida asosida - s qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi:

I play - he plays. Men o'ynadim - u o'ynadim.

3-shaxs birlikda to do, to go fe'llariga - es qo'shimchasi qo'shiladi:

He goes, he does.

2. Bo'lishsiz shakli asosiy fe'lning oldiga do (does) yordamchi fe'lini va not inkor yuklamasini qo'yish bilan yasaladi:

Ega + do (does) + not + V

I do not work. He does not work.

3. So'roq shakli do yordamchi fe'lini (3-shaxs birlikda does) egadan oldinga qo'yish bilan yasaladi:

Do I work? Does he (she) work? Men ishlaymanmi? U ishlaydimi?

Do + ega + V

Does

4. Og'zaki nutqda quyidagi qisqartirmalar qo'llaniladi:

I don't work

He (she, it) doesn't work

We (you, they) don't work

Use Present simple tense (Oddiy hozirgi zamonning ishlatilishi)

1. Present Simple odatiy, doimiy, egaga xos bo'lgan yoki umuman yuz beradigan ish-harakatini ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi (hozir emas):

The postman brings us the newspaper in the morning.

Pochtachi bizga gazetani ertalab olib keladi (odatiy harakat).

John walks to school every day. Jon har kun maktabga piyoda boradi.

The earth goes round the sun. Yer Quyosh atrofi da aylanadi.

An atheist doesn't believe in God. Ateist xudoga ishonmaydi.

What does this word mean? Bu so'z qanday ma'noni bildiradi?

He lives in Tashkent. U Toshkentda yashaydi. (doimiy).

He speaks French well. U fransuz tilida yaxshi gapiradi.

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2. Ingliz tilida davom zamonlarda ishlatilmaydigan to see, to recognize, to want, to understand kabi fe'llar bor. Bunday fe'llar bilan hozir, gapirilayotgan paytda davom etayotgan ish harakatni ifodalash uchun Present Continuous emas, Present Simple ishlatiladi.

I see a ship in the distance. Men uzoqda kemani ko'rayapman.

Don't talk so loudly, I hear you well. Buncha qattiq gapirma, seni yaxshi eshitayapman.

I don't understand this sentence. Men bu gapni tushunmayapman.

3. If agar, unless agar...- masa, provided that bo'lsa, shartda, when - da, paytida, before oldin, until -maguncha, till -gacha as soon as -gach, as long as - da kabi bog'lovchilar bilan bog'langan shart va payt ergash gaplarda Present Simple Simple Future o'rnida kelasi zamondagi ish-harakatni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi:

If he comes, I shall ask him about it. Agar u kelsa, men undan bu haqda so'rayman.

I shall go there unless it rains. Agar yomg'ir yog'masa, men u yerga boraman.

I shall stay here until he returns. U qaytib kelmaguncha, men shu yerda bo'laman.

We shall send you the documents as soon as we receive them from London.²

Biz hujjatlarni Londondan olishimiz bilanoq, ularni sizga yuboramiz.

4. Harakatni (qatnovni) ifodalaydigan to leave jo'namoq, tark etmoq, to start jo'namoq, to sail suzib ketmoq, to return qaytib kelmoq, to arrive yetib kelmoq, to go bormoq, to come kelmoq kabi fe'llar bilan Present Simple kelasi zamondagi ish-harakatni ifodalaydi. Bunda kelasi zamanni ko'rsatuvchi payt holi bo'lishi kerak:

Does your brother arrive on Monday? Akangiz dushanba kuni yetib keladimi?

The steamer sails tomorrow. Paroxod ertaga suzib ketadi.

Xulosa qilinsa, Present Simple — hozirgi oddiy zamonida odamlarning odatlari va boshqa muntazam faoliyati (davriylik muhim), shuningdek, ilmiy faktlar va har doim haqiqat bo'lgan narsalari haqida gap yuritiladi.

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² <https://learnenglish.urdu.uz/site/post?id=17>